

Project Title	Blue-Cloud 2026: A federated European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters
Project Acronym	Blue-Cloud 2026
Project Number	101094227
Type of project	RIA – Research and Innovation Action
Topics	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01
Starting date of Project	01 January 2023
Duration of the project	42 months
Website	www.blue-cloud.org

D2.7 – Tuning between Blue-Cloud Data Lakes and DTO development, 2nd report

Work Package	WP2 FAIR compliant Discovery and Access services for marine domains & beyond
Task	T2.4 Integration of Blue-Cloud data lakes with DTO developments
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Peer reviewers	Dick Schaap (MARIS)
Version	V2.0
Due Date	28/02/2025
Submission Date	30/06/2026

Dissemination Level

X	PU: Public
	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)
	EU-RES. Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
	EU-CON. Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)
	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)

Version History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.1	13/11/2024	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT), Pasquale Pagano (CNR-ISTI), Dick Schaap (MARIS), Marina Tonani (MOI)	Draft ToC
0.2	14/11/2023	Kate Larkin, Conor Delaney	Sections 2.1 and 2.2 Blue-Cloud role with respect to EMODnet
0.3	10/12/2024	Mathis Bertin, Marina Tonani (MOI)	Chapter 3 Blue-Cloud role with regard to EDITO and Annexes
0.4	13/12/2024	Pasquale Pagano (CNR-ISTI)	Revision of chapters 1.1 and 1.2
0.5	16/12/2024	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)	Introduction and conclusions, overall revision
0.6	17/12/2024	Dick Schaap (MARIS)	Edited Sections 2.1 and 2.2 Blue-Cloud positioning with respect to EMODnet
0.7	18/12/2025	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)	Final version for internal review by the Steering Board
0.8	09/01/2025	Kate Larkin, Conor Delaney	Edited Section 2.2 Blue-Cloud positioning with respect to EMODnet
	10/01/2025	Julia Vera	Overall review and edits, including to Chapter 3 and Annex
0.9	23/01/2025	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)	Addressed comments and completed final version
1.0	30/01/2025	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)	Clean final version
1.1	28/02/2026	Victoria Persson (MOI), Julia Vera (SSBE)	Version updated following validation of project EOSC Ocean & Waters Node.

1.2	19/06/2026	Victoria Persson, Marina Tonani (MOi)	Additional comments accounted for.
1.3	26/06/2026	Dick Schaap (MARIS)	Review of the document
2.0	29/06/2026	Pasquale Pagano (CNR)	Upload and submission of the deliverable

Keywords

EOSC; EDITO, EMODnet, Thematic Node

Disclaimer

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101094227. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.

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1. Introduction and context of this document

By working closely with long-term EU marine data services (i.e., EMODnet and Copernicus Marine), and research data infrastructures (i.e., EuroArgo, SeaDataNet, Ecotaxa and others), Blue-Cloud is introducing a federated model, offering e-infrastructure services (computing, storage, analytics, SSO, AAI, generic service), a data discovery service (10M+ datasets and products from European marine infrastructures), and research intensive virtual labs, embedded in a VRE open to any users with federated identity.

Blue-Cloud effectively piloted a marine thematic node within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), supporting high-quality marine science and contributing to the European Digital Twin Ocean programme and its implementing facilities. In parallel, it fostered a strong collaborative framework to support and contribute to the European Digital Twin Ocean initiative, EDITO.

Building on the success of this pilot phase, the established infrastructure and community have since evolved and are now officially recognized as the **EOSC Node | European Digital Twin Ocean** — a core component of the EOSC Federation dedicated to advancing and supporting the marine and water research communities.

The implementation and operationalisation of this thematic EOSC Node is being further advanced through the **EOSC Marine project**, which aims to establish the EOSC Node | European Digital Twin Ocean as a sustainable entry point to marine and freshwater data, services, computing resources and virtual research environments within the EOSC Federation. By building upon the foundations laid by Blue-Cloud and leveraging key European marine infrastructures and services, EOSC Marine will strengthen interoperability, accessibility and uptake of marine research resources across Europe.

At the same time, the EOSC node will continue to support the EC Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters", its work programme and the development of the European Digital Twin Ocean, which aims to model the ocean's multiple components, provide knowledge and understanding of the past and present, and create trustworthy predictions of its future behaviour. In this context, the EOSC node will contribute to strengthening the links between EDITO, the public infrastructure supporting the European DTO, and EOSC, while the EOSC Marine project further advances the integration of marine research services within the EOSC Federation.

A first version of this document was prepared and released early February 2025 in response to a request of DG RTD, DG MARE and DG DEFIS to clarify the positioning of Blue-Cloud with regard to EMODnet, EDITO and EOSC, on how the outputs of Blue-Cloud could be offered as key resources in operational services e.g., EMODnet, EDITO, EOSC Marine Node, and how Blue-Cloud could act as a marine thematic node and link to the EOSC, including promoting in EOSC the exploitation of EMODnet and Copernicus Marine Service data via the EDITO catalogue, as well as potentially other EDITO services and products. The first release has contributed to the EU decisioning process on the future of Blue-Cloud to become the **EOSC Node | European Digital Twin Ocean**. The current version of this document includes an updating of earlier thinking and details the pathway forward. To compile this document, in total 3 meetings of the DTO Task Force took place within the Blue-Cloud 2026 project. The minutes of those meetings have been added as annexes.

2. Blue-Cloud role with respect to EOSC

2.1. Overview of Blue-Cloud as a Thematic marine Node for EOSC: a “Factory” for marine science

The Blue-Cloud infrastructure and community will transform into the **EOSC node | European Digital Twin Ocean (DTO)**. Originating from the technology and ideas piloted in the Blue-Cloud2026 project, this EOSC node is to become a state-of-the-art cyber platform designed to implement an incubator of new research ideas. Functioning as a “factory” for marine science, this node supports scientists and researchers in designing, testing, and evaluating innovative computational analytical flows that extract valuable knowledge from diverse datasets, while accelerating open science and collaborative research in support of the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters.

Managed by CNR and powered by the D4Science e-infrastructure, the Node leverages EOSC Core capabilities—including Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting (AAI), monitoring, and a helpdesk—to optimise the user experience and support efficient collaboration.

It offers a comprehensive environment for sharing data, tools, and knowledge, fostering a “**web of scientific insight**” that creates a federation of relevant data sources for the entire EOSC community. By integrating advanced analytical tools, robust computing resources, and diverse datasets from observations and models, the platform empowers researchers to tackle complex ocean challenges and enhances the scientific community's ability to understand and predict marine phenomena. The Node offers a suite of common services and tools, including cloud storage, collaborative workspaces, **RStudio**, **JupyterLab**, and **Galaxy**, alongside a Software Importer and an Analytics Engine. These tools empower researchers to create and manage **Virtual Laboratories (VLabs)** and **Thematic Services**, facilitating seamless collaboration by enabling the efficient sharing of research artefacts.

The EOSC Federation **will consist of multiple EOSC Nodes** that are interconnected and can collaborate to share and manage scientific data, knowledge, and resources within and across thematic and geographical research communities.

The **EOSC Nodes will be entry points for users to the EOSC Federation**, with each node offering its own and possibly third-party services, including data reposing and accessing services.

As the decision-making body for EOSC, **the EOSC Tripartite Governance oversees the structure, governance and operations of the EOSC Federation.**

More info on the [EOSC website](#).

Figure 1 - Building the EOSC federation: vision from the EOSC Tripartite group, October 2024

The Node is evolving to provide a data discovery and access service component of EDITO (European Digital Twin Ocean), to deliver FAIR open data and analytical services into the EOSC Federation. This innovative approach enhances the EOSC ecosystem by providing a flexible and user-friendly platform for data-intensive applications and reproducible workflows. Building on the strengths of the Blue-Cloud consortium, EU Research Infrastructures and e-infrastructures, as well as technical and scientific partners, are now establishing the EOSC node | European Digital Twin Ocean. This represents the transition from a candidate node to a fully operational, federated thematic node (achieving TRL 9), ensuring compliance with EOSC federation rules, providing quality service, and implementing a long-term sustainability plan within the EDITO framework.

2.2. Blue-Cloud positioning towards EOSC

The positioning of the Blue-Cloud framework—now as **EOSC node | European Digital Twin Ocean**—is defined by "**Leveraging Smart Federation and Tripartite Governance for Scalable Research Impact**". The **EOSC Federation** is a horizontal, trusted "**System of Systems**" where multiple nodes are interconnected to share scientific resources. Under the **Tripartite Governance** model, which involves the European Commission, the EOSC Steering Board, and the EOSC Association, the Node ensures strategic alignment and community buy-in to prevent the creation of scientific silos.

Crucially, **Blue-Cloud is not an environment for depositing new data collections**. Instead, it is committed to ensuring that new research products generated in its VRE flow into relevant EU data services, such as **EMODnet** and **Copernicus Marine Service**, or EDITO, as/when applicable, thereby contributing to co-developing and growing the European Digital Twin Ocean via EDITO. Blue-Cloud's activities are designed to support and augment the existing marine knowledge infrastructure, ensuring that data flows seamlessly from European Research Infrastructures to end-users via existing aggregators (e.g., the **EDITO Catalogue**) without imposing access restrictions. Furthermore, Blue-Cloud is a promoter of initiatives that integrate and harmonise data, working on **federating multiple Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs)**—such as **SeaDataNet**, **EuroArgo**, and **EuroBIS**—to strengthen their **FAIRness**. This includes semantic support through the adoption of common vocabularies and ensuring that metadata is machine-actionable according to the **EOSC Interoperability Framework**.

According to the **Requirements for EOSC Nodes**, the DTO Node serves as a primary entry point for end-users to the entire **EOSC Federation**. In compliance with the EOSC Federation's common rules, the Node offers its own services alongside "third-party" services—onboarded via consolidated procedures—ensuring adherence to **FAIR principles** and recognised standards. These include curated research outputs (publications, datasets, software), specialised knowledge, applications, tools, and data processing capabilities. By transitioning to a fully operational status (**TRL 9**), the Node ensures comprehensive support for marine research within a "**web of scientific insight**."

Blue-Cloud already implements key federation mechanisms, such as **identity federation (AAI)** and shared accounting and monitoring, which are core operational requirements in EOSC. This enables valuable feedback on the integration of EOSC's resources and fosters a community of marine research infrastructures and open science practices within the **EOSC EU Node**. Blue-Cloud is in continuous strategic alignment with leading EC marine initiatives—**EMODnet**, **Copernicus Marine**, and the **EDITO** infrastructure—to ensure the Thematic EOSC marine node is representative of European marine knowledge services.

A cornerstone of this positioning is the **Smart Federation** model, which will aim to ensure technical interoperability and bi-directional integration between the Blue-Cloud VRE (**D4Science**) and the EDITO infrastructure (**Datalab**), providing EOSC users with discovery and access to cloud-optimised EC data services.

Currently, the Blue-Cloud Collaborative Data Analytics as a Service, functioning as a "Factory" for marine science, offers communities a tailored virtual laboratory equipped with a comprehensive suite of tools, including **Jupyter-based notebooks**, **RStudio** environments, **Galaxy**, and a scalable cloud computing platform. These solutions are customizable in terms of computing power, storage, and integrated data spaces. By seamlessly integrating these tools, the service fosters collaboration and accelerates the adoption of open science, allowing researchers to share analytical methods, reproduce findings, and publish complete experimental setups. These analytics environment instances abstract away the complexities of provisioning resources, empowering researchers to focus on scientific discovery and addressing critical ocean challenges under the **EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters**. Any EOSC user can request a specialised data analytics environment, which is governed by community-established access policies and managed through usage quotas and performance metrics to ensure sustainable growth.

By exploiting the Blue-Cloud VRE services, specialised workbenches and thematic marine services are accessible to the marine community. In particular, three workbenches for selected **Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs)** in physics, chemistry, and biology are being delivered in **Blue-Cloud 2026** through the collaboration of scientists and IT specialists. Efficient workflows allow scientists to integrate, harmonise, and validate large in situ datasets from different **Blue Data Infrastructure (BDI)** sources. Moreover, the adoption of FAIR digital assets guarantees data traceability, provenance preservation, and process replicability. These teams are implementing workflow components in **ARCO (Analysis-Ready Cloud-Optimised)** formats, increasing their Technology Readiness Level for full interoperability with the **EDITO framework**. These workbenches and their resulting EOVS collections are crucial for assessing the state of the marine environment and for the initialisation and validation of model simulations within **EDITO**.

Among the marine thematic services, the DTO Node currently provides access to the following virtual laboratories (VLabs):

- **The Global Fisheries Atlas VLab:** Provides a single, FAIR-compliant entry point for users to discover and understand the state of stocks and fisheries worldwide. It combines the **Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF)** with the **Global Tuna Atlas**, integrating datasets relevant to fisheries variables and supporting **UN SDG Indicator 14.4.1**.
- **The Zoo and Phytoplankton EO VLab:** provides descriptions of the current state of plankton communities and forecasts their evolution, offering valuable information for modelling and managing marine ecosystems.
- **The Carbon-Plankton Dynamics VLab:** analyses the drivers of phytoplankton dynamics, integrating carbon information to understand interactions between nutrients, productivity, and organic matter exchanges with the atmosphere and rivers.
- **The Marine Environmental Indicators VLab:** offers tools to generate and analyse indicators on environmental quality, ocean patterns, and carbon using big data analysis and machine learning methods developed in Jupyter Notebooks.
- **The Integration of Coastal Ocean Observations VLab:** combines data from **JERICO-RI** with other sources to gain insights into Europe's coastal ocean environments through advanced processing facilities and interactive visualisations.
- **The Coastal Currents from Observations VLab:** integrates ocean surface current maps from HF radar, drifter data, and satellite altimetry using the **DIVAnd** method, supporting simulations like the **MEDSLIK-II** oil spill model.

Additionally, the Node plays a crucial role as a **training environment** for new data scientists and analysts. By providing a platform for education and skill development, the DTO Node helps cultivate the next generation of experts who will drive future advancements in marine research and data analysis within the federated European ecosystem.

3. Blue-Cloud role with respect to EMODnet

3.1. Overview of EMODnet

The European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) is the European Commission (EC) *in situ* marine data service of the EC Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (EC DG MARE) and funded by the European Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund. Established in 2009, EMODnet plays a pivotal role as a trusted source of *in situ* marine environmental and human activities data and data products, serving a diverse user base across various sectors.

The EMODnet Portal (emodnet.ec.europa.eu) is a single access point to all EMODnet services, providing easy and free access to a wealth of marine data, metadata, and data products. Covering seven disciplinary

themes – bathymetry, geology, physics, chemistry, biology, seabed habitats and human activities – EMODnet spans the entire marine environment from coast to open ocean, surface to deep seafloor, whilst also offering data and information on the Blue Economy operations, from vessel density and offshore platform sightings, to hosting EU Member State Maritime Spatial Plans.

In collaboration with over 120 partner organizations and stakeholders, EMODnet aggregates data into Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) pan-European data layers, with data and accompanying metadata harmonized according to EU e.g., INSPIRE and International e.g., ISO standards. In addition, EMODnet experts produce unique data products such as EUSeaMap, a broad-scale seabed habitat map, the EU Digital Terrain Model for harmonized bathymetry, and the pan-European Marine Litter Database. EMODnet also offers a public Data Ingestion service to expand and diversify the data offer, supporting data collection efforts and data providers to submit their data for integration into EMODnet.

The start of the marine knowledge pipeline into EMODnet are ocean observations from Europe's diverse *in situ* ocean observation community. This includes data collection efforts of European projects and European Research Infrastructures, among others. In these cases, *in situ* ocean observation and primary data should be made available in EMODnet at the earliest possible opportunity, with the data pipeline in each case being a direct connection from the data provider to EMODnet.

3.2. Blue-Cloud positioning with respect to EMODnet

EMODnet is the EC *in situ* marine data service. Its portal gives a single access point to a wealth of marine data, metadata, and data products serving a wide and increasing community of users. Publishing is done by means of central product catalogue, map viewer, and subsetting (ERDDAP) services. In addition, the EMODnet portal gives a range of web services which can be used by users for setting up machine-to-machine exchanges. In practice, the data and metadata are brought together and harmonised cooperating with leading EU data management infrastructures such as SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, and EGDI, that manage European wide networks reaching out to many data originators in different disciplines. They also tap into EU Research Infrastructures such as EuroArgo and EcoTaxa, EuroGOOS and the international ICES data centre. The gathered metadata and data, following prevailing standards, are used by the EMODnet thematic groups for generating an increasing portfolio of data products, such as validated and harmonised data collections, a multitude of thematic maps, and other products like e.g. a Digital Terrain Model for all European seas.

Blue-Cloud operates its VRE as an open science platform and a series of analytical workflows have been developed as V Labs and Work Benches. Moreover, Blue-Cloud is open and invites external researchers to

develop new analytical workflows, making use of the available data from leading repositories, and supported by computational services. These activities will be continued by Blue-Cloud's successor – the EOSC node | European Digital Twin Ocean. Like Blue-Cloud, the EOSC node can be considered as an incubator for new analytical workflows as well as for generating new marine data products. If delivered with proven quality, new data products might be fit for inclusion in the EMODnet offer and EMODnet publishing services, while new analytical workflows might be interesting for uptake by EMODnet thematic groups. This concept of transfer between Blue-Cloud and EMODnet can be illustrated by the example of the Blue-Cloud WorkBench for EOVs concerning eutrophication. This WorkBench has been developed by chemical experts from EMODnet Chemistry and Copernicus Marine, combining their expertise on chemistry data quality control and data management. They worked together with IT experts, bringing in their expertises on big data handling, data merging and harmonisation, and semantic analysis and mapping. These qualities are needed because a major challenge of the WorkBench is to merge data sets from multiple repositories, which include potential duplicates and have different formats and semantics. Recently, the WorkBench has delivered a high-quality EOv data collection for eutrophication, including standard metadata, which is fit for publishing by EMODnet Chemistry. Moreover, the EMODnet Chemistry team is interested in adopting the WorkBench for future updates of the EOv product as part of its operations. Considering the current Blue-Cloud portfolio there might be more potential candidates for uptake by EMODnet. In particular in the biology domain there are several developments with such potential as new data products and/or adoption of the analytical workflows. In the perspective of the Blue-Cloud becoming the EOSC node | European Digital Twin Ocean in the EOSC ecosystem, it can be expected that more researchers with innovative ideas will find their way to the Blue-Cloud VRE, resulting in more results which can enrich the EMODnet product offer and its methods for generating and maintaining those products.

Another aspect of the relation EMODnet – Blue-Cloud is data provision. EMODnet is the leading European data service for assembling, standardising and publishing marine environmental and human activities data and data products at pan-European scale. These data originate from the European in situ ocean observation community which is incredibly large and diverse, with EMODnet having over 600 data aggregators and countless more data providers from research and academia, monitoring for EU Directives, private sector, civil society, citizen science and more. This includes EMODnet working together with EU data management infrastructures which have large and EU wide networks and proven standards, tools and services for managing and giving access to marine observation data sets. These infrastructures channel the data workflows from originators to EMODnet thematic groups. In addition, EMODnet operates EMODnet Ingestion which aims at identifying, convincing and connecting new data owners to share their data with EMODnet. There are two modes in use: mode 1 concerns new data providers making use of the EMODnet Submission service for manually entering and submitting their data contributions.

These submissions are then reviewed and processed, where possible, by the EMODnet Ingestion network for possible inclusion into EMODnet. Mode 2 concerns establishing automatic connections for data exchange. This concerns a cooperation of EMODnet Ingestion with EMODnet Physics for connecting new operational oceanography stations and networks at NRT level. It also concerns coupling other data repositories in an automatic way, which is the case currently for the SeaDataNet SeaNoe data publishing service.

As an operational service of the EC, EMODnet already has functioning public and free Data Services, including a Products Catalogue and a Map Viewer. Within the Blue-Cloud project, a separate Data Discovery & Access service (DD&AS) has been developed which has proved useful to serve the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environments and to extend the current federation of infrastructures that are not yet connected into EMODnet. Blue-Cloud has contributed to improving and optimising the web services and content of multiple marine RIs not yet included in the data provision of EMODnet. The work concerned the following RIs: EMSO, ENA-EBI, MGNIFY, SIOS, SOCAT, ICOS. They have undertaken actions for upgrading their web services and further populating their contents, in support of more streamlined discovery and access and facilitating a common core metadata profile, well supported by controlled vocabularies. The Blue-Cloud DD&AS has been used to test and monitor the progress of the RIs in making their services and output more FAIR.

The multiple common partners in EMODnet and Blue-Cloud provide an opportunity to take forward partnerships and developments of the EOSC DTO Node e.g., regarding data flows and to apply these to EMODnet, to strengthen and diversify the data offer in EMODnet.

At the time of the Blue-Cloud pilot project and the initiation of the second (Blue-Cloud 2026) project, EDITO was a concept. At this point in time there was no central service to discover EMODnet and Copernicus Marine Service data in one place. However, during 2023-2024, EDITO has delivered a common Data Lake (EDITO-Infra) underpinning the official European Digital Twin Ocean. Going forward, the EDITO Data Lake is the official gateway to EMODnet and Copernicus Marine Service data.

Blue-Cloud has undertaken activities aimed at bringing FAIRness, interoperability, and machine-actionability to the data services as managed by Research Infrastructures. The successor EOSC node | European Digital Twin Ocean will give a follow-up directed towards making the metadata, data, and services of Research Infrastructures fit for uptake in the data pipelines of EMODnet, which then also will benefit the EDITO Data Lake.

4. Blue-Cloud role with regard to EDITO

4.1. About EDITO

The EDITO platform^{1,2} constitutes the public infrastructure platform underpinning the European Digital Twin Ocean. Developed under the EDITO-Infra (2022–2025) and EDITO2 (2025–2028) projects, it is designed to evolve into a long-term European infrastructure supporting the objectives of the EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”.

Led by Mercator Ocean International in partnership with VLIZ, and Seascope Belgium, on behalf of Copernicus Marine and EMODnet, EDITO integrates and upgrades core European marine data and service infrastructures into a unified digital framework. It combines ocean observations, model outputs, analytical tools and high-performance computing resources, enabling the development of digital twins, applications and “what-if” scenarios.

EDITO provides a Virtual Research Environment (Datalab) supporting the development, execution and sharing of applications and workflows. It is built on open standards and interoperable architectures, ensuring alignment with European data governance principles and enabling integration with external infrastructures. Its catalogue relies on standardised metadata approaches and machine-to-machine interfaces to facilitate discoverability and reuse of marine data assets.

In its second phase, EDITO strengthens user support, expands onboarding processes for new data and services, and enhances modelling and application development capabilities, consolidating its role as the core infrastructure of the European Digital Twin Ocean ecosystem.

¹ <https://www.edito.eu/>

² <https://datalab.dive.edito.eu/>

Figure 2 - An overview of the EDITO technical offer to service the needs of DTO development

4.2. Blue-Cloud positioning towards EDITO

Blue-Cloud’s successor EOSC node | European Digital Twin Ocean will act as an innovation incubator for marine research infrastructures, providing Virtual Research Environments (VREs) where scientists design and test analytical workflows and computational models. The EDITO platform can support the development of these applications, offering efficient data access and resources. The applications can then be deployed on EDITO for sustainability. As demonstrated at DOF 2024, Blue-Cloud (D4Science) users can bring their work to EDITO by either creating a service or a process. If their computation is already containerized, this is a straightforward process that is easily done following available documentation³. The method will then be catalogued on EDITO and run on EDITO. As part of Blue-Cloud 2026, concrete interoperability activities have been undertaken with EDITO to test cross-platform integration and long-term sustainability pathways.

4.2.1. Blue-Cloud applications onboarded in EDITO

Interoperability between Blue-Cloud (D4Science) and EDITO has been demonstrated through the onboarding of selected Virtual Laboratories (VLabs) and applications into the EDITO Datalab environment.

³ <https://docs.dive.edito.eu/>

- **VLab 5 – Global Fisheries Atlas:** selected RStudio and Shiny applications have been deployed within EDITO, demonstrating portability of containerised services and reuse of harmonised datasets.
- **VLab 3 – Carbon Plankton Dynamics:** the Nutrient–Phytoplankton–Zooplankton–Detritus (NPZD) ecosystem model has been fully onboarded into EDITO, enabling execution and further development within the EDITO infrastructure.
- **DTO Track application:** developed during a Blue-Cloud hackathon, this prototype digital twin application integrates fish tracking data and modelling outputs, combining Blue-Cloud analytical workflows with EDITO deployment capabilities.

These examples illustrate practical interoperability, demonstrating that computational workflows and applications developed in Blue-Cloud can be transferred to and sustained within EDITO.

4.2.2. Blue-Cloud – EDITO Interoperability current status

Several technical alignments already facilitate integration between Blue-Cloud and EDITO:

- Adoption of interoperable catalogue and metadata standards: EDITO conforms to the STAC specification that drives a uniform means for indexing assets, and follows the CF convention to name the variables inside its catalogue.
- Use of open APIs for process execution: EDITO exposes a process API that implements the OGC API Processes standard that is the same adopted by the Blue-Cloud VRE Analytics platform.
- Support for containerised computational workflows.

These shared principles enable exposure and execution of processes across platforms and provide a solid basis for deeper federation.

To further interoperability, in the transition from Blue-Cloud to EOSC node | European Digital Twin Ocean, identified enhancements include:

- Implementation of a generic method to “wrap” Blue-Cloud methods into EDITO processes, so the method will be catalogued on EDITO, can be launched from EDITO, but will run on Blue-Cloud.
- Exposure of Blue-Cloud’s method catalogue in EDITO’s process catalogue. Blue-Cloud’s methods will be exposed through EDITO’s API and can be launched programmatically from anywhere and will run on Blue-Cloud.
- For a seamless interoperability with Blue-Cloud, EDITO can use the EOSC’s SSO system, so that a user can easily use both platforms with one single account.

These elements form the technical foundation for structured federation and are further developed in the context of the recently confirmed EU-funded project EOSC Marine, aimed at developing the EOSC node | European Digital Twin Ocean.

4.2.3. EOSC Node | European Digital Twin Ocean development

The Horizon project EOSC Marine was accepted by the European Commission in January 2026. The project aims to develop further the EOSC node | European Digital Twin Ocean as an operational thematic node for marine research within the EOSC Federation, providing researchers with an EOSC compliant digital environment with access to core computing capabilities, coupled with multidisciplinary datasets and workflows from in-situ and earth observations, models, and analytical tools and services that are essential for responding to the needs and objectives defined by the EC Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030”. The EOSC Marine project directly builds upon the achievements from the Blue-Cloud 2026 project and the EDITO programme. This combination will evolve the EOSC node | European Digital Twin Ocean into the component of EDITO that delivers EOSC FAIR Open data and analytical services instrumental for deepening research of the ocean, European seas, coastal and inland waters.

The leading principle of the EOSC node | European Digital Twin Ocean is to enhance and combine services and resources from EDITO with services and resources developed in the Blue-Cloud and Blue-Cloud 2026 projects, while fulfilling the EOSC Federation requirements. The aim is the inclusion of the output data of a selection of aquatic environmental Research infrastructures (RI) in the EDITO Catalogue, through CMEMS or EMODnet when suitable and otherwise directly in EDITO. The EDITO DataLab and the Virtual Research Environments (VRE) of Blue-Cloud will be connected through a seamless e-infrastructure with Single-Sign-On (SSO) for building, running and sharing of analytical processes and orchestrating complex and data intensive computations. EOSC researchers will be provided with data, algorithms, and computing resources, while it will mobilise and make available for EDITO major additional computing resources.

Blue-Cloud 2026 and EDITO are currently distinct systems that function as a “candidate” node - not as fully integrated and EOSC-compliant federated assets. The ambition of the EOSC Marine project is to transition the node beyond its candidate stage, formalizing and evolving it into an operational, federated EOSC component. This requires implementing a smart federation between the Blue-Cloud VRE and the EDITO infrastructure, a challenge that involves aligning existing services with the evolving specifications of the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF).

4.2.3.1. *Interoperability between the Virtual Research Environments of EDITO and Blue-Cloud, and with EOSC*

To this end, EDITO will, in the framework of the EOSC Marine project, contribute to the development and establishment of a smart federation and interoperability between the Virtual Research Environments of EDITO (Datalab) and Blue-Cloud (D4Science), as well as to the alignment of the e-infrastructure of the EOSC node | European Digital Twin Ocean with the EOSC EU Node reference architecture.

4.2.3.1.1. **Interoperability framework**

The interoperability potential will be analyzed and mapped, more specifically, a detailed analysis of the current authentication and authorization frameworks implemented in Blue-Cloud (D4Science) and EDITO (Datalab) will be conducted to identify similarities, differences, and potential gaps to enable secure and seamless user identity federation and access control across both platforms. A comprehensive list of processes available on both platforms will be compiled to enable analysis of process functionalities, inputs/outputs, and execution environments and to identify overlaps and complementarities. A technical design will be developed for exposing and integrating processes across platforms using OGC API Processes standard as the primary interface for process discovery and execution to define the specifications and communication protocols required for cross-platform interoperability.

4.2.3.1.2. **Blueprint for implementation of the interoperability framework**

A strategic blueprint will be created for the implementation of the interoperability framework and for integration in EOSC. The blueprint will build on the interoperable framework analysis and design described above. It will provide a structured roadmap for the operational integration of the Blue-Cloud and EDITO platforms. The blueprint will also outline mechanisms for alignment with EOSC Node requirements.

4.2.3.2. *FAIR & federated marine data services for EOSC*

Part of the EOSC Marine project is to make sure that data and services from leading European marine data services, including from Blue-Cloud and EDITO, are FAIR and federated.

Firstly, this includes ensuring that data model outputs from Blue-Cloud are fit for uptake in EDITO through EMODnet and CMEMS. To this end, machine-to-machine (M2M) services will be added to enable exporting of data in ARCO format with metadata, web services, and notebooks from Blue-Cloud RIs for uptake in the EMODnet, CMEMS, and EDITO catalogues.

Secondly, it includes evolving the EDITO Catalogue to align with EOSC principles and standards to ensure the assets are available for the Node research environments (RIs), including those of Blue-Cloud (D4Science).

Thirdly, it includes the provision of FAIR and analysis-ready marine data standards, best practices (e.g. for semantic interoperability), and services to EOSC. With regards to EDITO, a service template will be

developed (and integrated in Galaxy) for quickly viewing datasets within the EDITO STAC catalogue, and EDITO's R tools (e.g. RStudio) will be extended to access data from all the data lakes in the EOSC Node.

4.2.3.3. Governance structure and sustainability plan for EOSC node |European Digital Twin Ocean

As part of the EOSC Marine project, EDITO will participate in the formulation and establishment of the governance structure and sustainability plan for the EOSC node \ European Digital Twin Ocean, in the context of the EOSC and EDITO programmes.

This includes the conditions for federated technical governance of the Node. To this end, existing EDITO guidelines for onboarding and enrollment of new assets will be assessed versus guidelines and best practices for EOSC.

The sustainability plan will specify the necessary human, technological, and financial resources required for the node to provide access to core EU marine knowledge assets (EMODnet, CMEMS, EDITO) and RIS via EOSC beyond the project lifespan.

4.2.3.4. Summary of EDITO engagements for EOSC Node

To summarize, in the context of the EOSC Marine project, Blue-Cloud and EDITO will:

- Onboard into EDITO the Blue-Cloud outputs, such as workbenches, including for EOVs, and data from these.
- Assess the technical, semantic, and governance conditions required for the EDITO platform to achieve interoperability with EOSC, in alignment with the EOSC framework, policies, standards, and architectural principles outlined in the EOSC Federation Handbook.
- Analyse pathways for strengthening interoperability and two-way interaction between the Blue-Cloud platform (D4Science) and EDITO, building upon EOSC-aligned mechanisms as the primary integration reference layer.
- Produce a blueprint for federated integration between Blue-Cloud (D4Science) and EDITO (Datalab).
- Produce a long-term Governance scheme and sustainability plan for continued and effective technical collaboration of the marine Node with EOSC governance and EDITO.

Interoperability with EOSC is considered the foundational layer for cross-platform integration. Any additional technical or portal-level adaptations required to facilitate interoperability between D4Science and EDITO beyond EOSC-compliant alignment will be jointly evaluated, taking into account proportionality of effort, existing platform architectures, and the principle that platform-specific developments should be implemented within the respective system's governance and technical domain.

4.3. EDITO Task Force

The consolidation of the EOSC node |European Digital Twin Ocean will establish the conditions that can guide the transition towards becoming a core component of the EDITO programme, for long-term sustainability. These activities will be carried out in accordance with, and aligned to, the strategic and technical guidance provided by the Blue-Cloud 2026 “Digital Twin Ocean (DTO) Task Force”.

In line with European developments and the objectives of the European Commission, the EDITO Task Force aims and activities within the framework of Blue-Cloud 2026 WP2, have been extended to include precursor actions in preparation for the EOSC Marine project, which is expected to commence following the conclusion of Blue-Cloud2026. The renewed mandate of the DTO Task Force is to further structure the linkage between EOSC and EDITO.

To this end, four online meetings with a restricted number of participants were planned for the first half of 2026:

- Technical meeting#1 Authentication and Single Sign On EOSC-EDITO.
Attendance: technical team from CNR and from EDITO.
- Technical meeting#2 Service registration. Attendance: technical team from CNR and from EDITO.
- Technical meeting #3 Catalogue of resources. Attendance: technical team from CNR and from EDITO.
- Strategic meeting to define the policy for providing access to resources and the governance.
Attendance: coordination of EOSC Marine project, coordination and technical coordination of EDITO.

4.3.1. DTO Task Force Progress

As of June 2026, three of the four planned DTO Task Force meetings have been successfully organised and held. The corresponding meeting minutes are provided in Annexes X–Z.

The meetings brought together representatives from Blue-Cloud2026, EOSC, EDITO and associated technical teams to explore practical pathways for interoperability between the EOSC ecosystem and the European Digital Twin Ocean infrastructure.

The first meeting focused on Authentication and Single Sign-On (SSO) between EOSC and EDITO. Discussions confirmed that identity federation represents a foundational interoperability layer and that both infrastructures already rely on compatible technologies, notably Keycloak and OpenID Connect. The

participants agreed that the federation of identity providers should constitute the first concrete technical integration step between the two environments.

The second meeting addressed Service Registration and the exposure of EDITO capabilities within the EOSC ecosystem. Discussions clarified the EOSC service model, reviewed metadata requirements and explored technical options for synchronising service catalogues. Particular attention was given to the registration of EDITO services, processes and virtual research environments as discoverable EOSC resources.

The third meeting focused on the Catalogue of Data Products and Resources. Discussions examined publication workflows for Blue-Cloud datasets, interoperability between Blue-Cloud, EDITO, EMODnet and EOSC catalogues, and mechanisms for increasing discoverability while avoiding duplication of effort. The meeting highlighted the importance of leveraging existing infrastructures and identified Blue-Cloud as a potential facilitator of alignment between EOSC and EDITO catalogue frameworks.

Collectively, these meetings have provided a structured forum for technical exchange and have helped clarify several key aspects of future EOSC–EDITO interoperability, including identity federation, service exposure, metadata harmonisation and catalogue integration. The outcomes of these discussions are expected to inform the forthcoming EOSC Marine project, which will implement the EOSC Node | European Digital Twin Ocean.

4.3.2. Outcomes

The DTO Task Force meetings have provided a structured platform for bridging the ongoing Blue-Cloud2026 activities with the forthcoming EOSC Marine project and EDITO.

To date, the meetings have:

- Advanced technical discussions on authentication and identity federation between EOSC and EDITO, including agreement on Keycloak federation as an initial integration pathway;
- Clarified approaches for exposing EDITO services, processes and Virtual Research Environments through EOSC catalogues and service registration mechanisms;
- Initiated discussions on catalogue interoperability, metadata harmonisation and dataset discoverability across Blue-Cloud, EDITO, EMODnet and EOSC;
- Identified strategic considerations related to governance, resource onboarding and the avoidance of duplication across European marine data infrastructures.

While the meetings have not served as formal decision-making bodies, they have successfully consolidated alignment among the participating initiatives, clarified technical directions and established a common basis for future implementation activities under the EOSC Marine project for the EOSC Node | European Digital Twin Ocean.

5. Conclusions and next steps

The Digital Twin Ocean panorama in Europe is evolving at fast pace. The landscape in which the Blue-Cloud 2026 project operates has changed considerably since its initial launch. The European Science Cloud (EOSC) has seen significant evolution and, in parallel, the European Digital Twin Ocean was launched and EDITO deployed as its underpinning public infrastructure and intended to evolve into a long-term, sustained European infrastructure.

Ongoing dialogue and technical exchanges are required to elaborate on how interoperability can be established between the Blue-Cloud digital ecosystem and the EDITO infrastructure to achieve a dynamic exchange. The DTO Task Force meetings have clarified several key aspects of future EOSC–EDITO interoperability, which will be further elaborated in the forthcoming EOSC Marine project, which will start in September 2026, aiming at implementing the EOSC Node | European Digital Twin Ocean.

Annex 1

AI-Assisted Meeting Notes Disclaimer

The meeting notes contained in this annex were prepared with the assistance of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools. AI was used to support the transcription, structuring and summarisation of discussions based on notes taken during the meetings. The content has subsequently been reviewed, validated and, where necessary, corrected by the meeting organisers. While every effort has been made to ensure accuracy, these notes should be considered a summary of the discussions and are not intended to constitute a verbatim transcript.

Summary – DTO Task Force Technical Meeting

Date: 12 March 2026

Topic: EDITO–EOSC synchronisation with focus on Authentication and Single Sign-On (SSO)

Context: Blue-Cloud2026 Task 2.4 – Integration of Blue-Cloud data lakes with DTO developments.

1. Purpose of the meeting

- This was the first of three technical meetings dedicated to aligning EDITO, Blue-Cloud2026, and the EOSC EU Node.
- The main objective was to initiate technical discussions on authentication and SSO as the first step towards interoperability.
- These meetings aim to prepare integration between BC2026/EDITO and the EOSC EU DTO Node project.

Key Discussion Points

2. Identity federation between EDITO and EOSC

- A federation of identities is required so that:
 - Blue-Cloud users can access EDITO services, and
 - EDITO users can access Blue-Cloud/EOSC services using their EDITO identity.
- Identity federation is a core EOSC principle and enables future interoperability for:
 - AI services

- monitoring and accounting
- helpdesk and service integration.

3. EOSC federation status

- EOSC currently federates user identities but not services yet.
- Users connecting today typically access only the EOSC EU Node.
- The full federation of nodes is expected by the end of 2026, with initial federation operational around October.
- EOSC governance bodies involved:
 - Node Operational Committee
 - Coordinator Committee
 - Technical Working Groups

4. Architecture approach

- EOSC follows a “system of systems” model:
 - Each node remains independent.
 - Users can move between nodes using their digital identity.
- However, work environments may differ between nodes.

5. Authentication vs Authorization

A key distinction was made:

Authentication (SSO)

- Allows users to log in across platforms using the same identity.

Authorization

- Determines what resources a user can access.

- Resource governance remains local to each platform.

Example:

- A user authenticated via EOSC may still need approval to access EDITO resources.

6. Current identity infrastructure

Both platforms already use compatible technologies:

- Keycloak (identity management)
- OpenID Connect
- Proxy-based identity federation

Because both systems rely on Keycloak, federation should be relatively straightforward.

7. First concrete integration step

The group agreed that the first technical step will be to federate Keycloak instances between platforms.

Technical leads:

- Mauro (EOSC/D4Science side)
- Gabriel (EDITO/CMEMS side)

Testing environments exist on both sides.

8. Next operational actions

Agreed actions:

1. Create an activity in Blue-Cloud
2. Federate Keycloak between the two platforms
3. Exchange identity provider URLs and attributes
4. Open a technical issue via the AAI task force

5. Use staging environments for testing

A ticket can be created via D4Science support.

9. Future topics (not addressed yet)

Some complex issues were postponed to future work or the new EOSC DTO Node project, including:

- Cross-platform roles and authorization mapping
- Resource quotas and governance
- Federation with other EOSC nodes

10. Deliverable guidance

For the Blue-Cloud deliverable *D2.7 – Tuning between Blue-Cloud data lakes and DTO development 2nd Report*:

- Only report that the technical meetings are taking place.
- Do not wait for technical implementation results.

Key Takeaways

- SSO via Keycloak federation is the first integration step between EDITO and EOSC.
- Identity federation will allow users to access services across platforms with one digital identity.
- Authorization and resource governance will remain platform-specific.
- Initial implementation work will start via Blue-Cloud activities coordinated by Mauro and Gabriel.

Annex 2

AI-Assisted Meeting Notes Disclaimer

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DTO Task Force – Technical Meeting #2: Service Registration

Date: 18 March 2026
 Time: 10:00–11:00
 Format: Online (Microsoft Teams)

1. Objective of the Meeting

This second technical meeting of the DTO Task Force focused on service registration within EOSC, with the aim to:

- Clarify the definition of a “service” in the EOSC/DTO context
- Present the EOSC service catalogue approach
- Discuss metadata requirements and standards
- Explore integration options between EDITO and the EOSC DTO Node catalogue

2. Key Discussion Points

2.1 EOSC Service Catalogue – Overview

- EOSC aims to provide a federated catalogue of services, aggregated from different nodes.
- Each service is operated and managed by its provider, including:
 - Access rights

- Resource quotas
- The catalogue contains metadata entries linking to services, enabling discoverability across nodes.

2.2 Definition of a “Service”

- There is currently no strict or universally agreed definition of a service in EOSC.
- The concept remains flexible and evolving.

A service can include:

- Digital services (e.g. JupyterLab, RStudio, data repositories)
- Hybrid services (e.g. tools supporting Data Management Plans)
- Virtual Research Environments (VREs) and Virtual Labs (Vlabs)
- Provision of access to computing resources

Key

takeaway:

A service is not limited to a technical endpoint, but can represent a broader capability offered to users.

2.3 EOSC Service Metadata

EOSC defines a metadata framework (not fully standardised) to describe services.

Generic Metadata

- Title
- Description
- Tags
- Licence
- Visibility (generally public)
- Author (metadata creator)
- Maintainer (contact point)

Service-Specific Metadata

- Abbreviation
- Alternative identifier (e.g. DOI)
- Webpage (entry point to access the service)
- Logo
- Service provider(s)
- Scientific domain(s)
- Category (extensible list, e.g. “laboratory”)
- Target users
- Language
- Contact points
- Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
- Access policy
- Additional type/classification fields

👉 The metadata model is:

- Extensible
- Adaptable per node
- Not yet fully harmonised across EOSC

2.4 EOSC DTO Node Catalogue

- The DTO Node catalogue currently includes ~16 high-level services.
- Services can be described:
 - Individually
 - Or at aggregated catalogue level
- The catalogue is:

- Continuously harvested by EOSC
- Not yet public
- Nodes decide which services to expose.

2.5 Processes as Services

- EDITO “processes” (with inputs/outputs/APIs) can be considered services in EOSC.
- This aligns with practices already used in Blue-Cloud (BC).

2.6 Catalogue Synchronisation & Integration Options

Two main approaches discussed:

Option 1 – Push (EDITO → DTO Node)

- EDITO pushes metadata via API to DTO Node
- Advantages:
 - EDITO maintains full control over updates
 - Clear workflow
- Requirements:
 - Authentication & authorisation setup
 - Compliance with DTO metadata format (JSON profile)

Option 2 – Pull (DTO Node harvests EDITO catalogue)

- DTO Node harvests metadata from an EDITO endpoint
- Advantages:
 - Enables catalogue to always be up to date

👉 Preliminary preference (EDITO side):

- Prefer harvesting (pull model) via an EDITO endpoint

2.7 Technical Considerations

- EOSC expects:
 - One endpoint per node for harvesting
- DTO Node can provide:
 - Metadata specifications (JSON profile)
 - API for publishing services
 - Authentication/authorisation mechanisms
- Harvesting of DTO Node from EOSC is currently:
 - In testing phase
 - Expected to move to production soon

3. Key Takeaways

- The EOSC service model is flexible but not yet standardised
- A service can represent a wide range of capabilities, not just APIs
- Metadata-driven cataloguing is central to EOSC interoperability
- Integration between EDITO and EOSC will require:
 - Agreement on metadata structure
 - Decision on push vs pull architecture
- Technical alignment is progressing, with clear next steps identified

4. Decisions

- No formal decisions taken
 - General agreement on:
 - Moving forward with technical integration discussions
 - Exploring both push and pull approaches
-

5. Actions

- CNR (EOSC/DTO Node):
 - Share metadata specifications and JSON profile
 - Provide documentation for API integration
- EDITO (MOi / team):
 - Review integration options (push vs pull)
 - Prepare internal approach for exposing EDITO services
- Victoria Persson:
 - Invite Julia Vera to the next DTO Task Force meeting

Annex 3

AI-Assisted Meeting Notes Disclaimer

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Meeting Minutes

DTO Task Force – Technical Meeting 3

Topic: Catalogue of Data Products & Resources

Date: 30 March 2026

1. Participants

Technical teams from CNR and from EDITO.

2. Objective of the Meeting

The objective of this meeting was to discuss:

- The **publication workflows** for datasets generated within the Blue-Cloud project
- The **interoperability between Blue-Cloud, EDITO, EMODnet, and EOSC catalogues**
- The **discoverability of datasets and services across platforms**, in particular within EOSC

3. Key Discussion Points

3.1 Publication of Blue-Cloud Datasets

- Blue-Cloud workbenches (WB1, WB2, WB3) generate datasets that must be **published as open access**, in line with European Commission requirements.
- Some datasets (e.g. WB3) require an **embargo period** to allow scientific publication prior to public release.
- It was clarified that:
 - **Embargo ≠ private data**: datasets under embargo are identifiable (via persistent identifiers) but not accessible.
 - Blue-Cloud **does not act as a data repository**; instead, it relies on **trusted external repositories** (e.g. Zenodo).
 - The Blue-Cloud catalogue contains **metadata only**, pointing to datasets stored externally.

3.2 EDITO Data Management Approach

- EDITO provides:
 - A **data lake (object storage)** for dataset hosting
 - A **metadata catalogue (STAC-based)** for discoverability
- Key principles:
 - All datasets are **automatically registered in the catalogue** upon ingestion
 - Access rights can be managed (private / restricted / public)
 - Data must be **validated before being made public**

3.3 Interoperability Between Blue-Cloud and EDITO

- Consensus emerged that:
 - **Duplication should be avoided**
 - Existing infrastructures (especially **EMODnet pipelines into EDITO**) should be leveraged
- For WB1 and WB2:
 - Data can follow **existing EMODnet ingestion workflows → EDITO**

- For WB3:
 - More complex case (EMODnet Biology)
 - Identified as a **test case for onboarding external datasets into EDITO**

3.4 Data Discoverability and “Promotion”

- “Promoting” a dataset was clarified as:
 - Making datasets **discoverable via catalogues**, regardless of storage location
- EOSC vision:
 - A **federated discovery layer** where users can search across datasets, services, and resources
 - Focus on **metadata aggregation**, not data storage
- Key discussion points:
 - EDITO and EMODnet already provide **open, interoperable catalogues (via APIs/endpoints)**
 - Concern raised about **potential duplication of effort within EOSC**
 - Need to ensure EOSC leverages existing catalogues rather than recreating them

3.5 EOSC Integration Challenges

- EOSC currently defines **specific standards and protocols** (e.g. OAI-PMH, metadata profiles) for onboarding repositories
- Challenges identified:
 - Existing systems (EDITO, EMODnet) use **different standards**
 - Limited flexibility in EOSC to adapt to external standards
- Two possible approaches:
 1. **Align with EOSC requirements**
 2. **Promote existing EDITO/EMODnet standards within EOSC**
- Role of Blue-Cloud:

- Potential **mediator between EDITO and EOSC**
- Support alignment and integration efforts

3.6 Strategic Considerations

- Question raised on **added value of EOSC discoverability** for already well-known datasets (e.g. Copernicus, EMODnet)
- Need to clarify:
 - What datasets/services should be exposed to EOSC
 - What added value EOSC provides beyond existing platforms
- Agreement that this topic requires:
 - **Further dedicated discussion (technical + governance level)**

4. Key Conclusions

- Blue-Cloud datasets can be:
 - **Published via EDITO**, leveraging EMODnet workflows where applicable
- WB3 identified as a **pilot case for testing ingestion into EDITO**
- Dataset “promotion” = **catalogue-level discoverability via metadata**
- EOSC integration remains **unclear and requires further analysis**
- Avoiding duplication and leveraging existing infrastructures is a **shared priority**

5. Actions

- **MOi**
 - Organise a **follow-up meeting** on EOSC discoverability and catalogue interoperability
 - Organise the **4th DTO Task Force meeting** (including governance aspects)
 - Provide **documentation on EDITO catalogues and APIs**
- **Blue-Cloud Team**

-
- Provide **documentation on catalogue standards and EOSC requirements**
 - Contact Workbench leaders (WB1–WB3) and guide them toward EDITO onboarding via user support
-

6. Next Steps

- Further meeting to:
 - Clarify **EOSC requirements and expectations**
 - Identify **relevant datasets/services for EOSC exposure**
 - Define **technical pathways for interoperability**
-